

Synthesis of some New Quinazolin-4(3H)-ones as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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Substituted-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones have been reported to possess various biological activities¹. In continuation of earlier work on 2,3-disubstituted-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones², some new compounds have been synthesised and screened for their antimicrobial activities.

Phenylacetylchloride gave *o*-(phenylacetyl)aminobenzoic acid (1) on reaction with anthranilic acid. Cyclisation of 1 in presence of acetic anhydride gave 2-phenylmethyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-ones (2) which on condensation with primary aromatic amines gave 2-phenylmethyl-3-arylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones (3).

Compound 3d was found to be active against *Salmonella typhi* and 3a and 3h were active against *Bacillus subtilis*. However, rest of the compounds failed to show any appreciable antibacterial activity. Antifungal study reveals compounds 3d and 3i to be active against *Alternaria alternata* and compound 3g active against *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Antimicrobial study shows that in quinazolin-4(3H)-ones, the substitution of the phenyl ring at position-3 by *m*-OH, *m*-NO₂ and *p*-Br produces remarkable activity.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries using a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G using hex-

ane-ethanol-chloroform (1 : 3 : 6). Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 470 spectrophotometer.

o-(Phenylacetyl)aminobenzoic acid (1) : It was prepared following known procedure of acetylation³ with the following modifications. A mixture of phenylacetic acid (0.06 mol) and PCl₅ (0.06 mol) was triturated. To phenyl acetyl chloride thus formed, anthranilic acid (0.06 mol) was added with trituration, followed by water. The resulting solid was washed with hot water and crystallised from ethanol, (55%), m.p. 178–79°.

2-Phenylmethyl-3-(substituted)quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (3a-h) : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.05 mol) was refluxed under anhydrous condition for 4–6 h. The excess acetic anhydride was then distilled off under reduced pressure and cooled to room temperature. The intermediate 2 so obtained as a solid mass was used up immediately for the next step.

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and primary aromatic amines (0.01 mol) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 4–6 h. After cooling, the contents were poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solids were washed with distilled water, dried and crystallised from hot 95% ethanol (yields 48–68%) : 3a m.p. 145–46°; b, 160–62°; c, 133–35°; d, 138–39°; e, 164–65°; f, 153–55°; g, 158–60°; h, 168–70°; ν_{\max} 1 670–1 645 (NC=O), 1 450–1 430 (CH₂–C=C) and 1 600–1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=N). All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Biological activities : Antimicrobial activity was evaluated by filter paper disc agar diffusion method⁵. For antibacterial studies Hi-media bacteriological nutrient broth and bacteriological nutrient agar were used against Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli*. Antifungal studies were carried out using Sabouraud's dextrose broth and dextrose agar against *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria alternata* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. Dimethylformamide was used for solubilising the compounds and also for control studies. The concentration of the compounds taken was 1 mg ml⁻¹. Norfloxacin (1 mg ml⁻¹) and clotrimazole (1 mg ml⁻¹) were used as standards for bacterial and fungal studies respectively.

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